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Open Content Development as a Challenge and an Opportunity (Hungarian Case)

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Abstract

This paper informs about a Hungarian initiative on the innovation for the collaborative content construction process as a new methodological learning development model. The objective aim is to apply our unique concept to modernize the methodology used in vocational teacher training and practical training by creating complex learning content units. In the frame of elaborating online teaching materials, we used learning units and micro-contents as new tools. The research and development based on the recognition of creating open learning materials become in high demand in VET systems worldwide. Our project focused on local innovation where vocational teachers play an essential role. Furthermore, we realized that the new mobile communication environment based on networks and cloud services offers new applications daily for evaluation and analysis of the learning resources and micro-contents created via collaborative pedagogical activity.

Keywords

collaborative content development, micro-content, online teaching, vocational teachers

1 Elaboration of online teaching materials: micro-contents as a new tool

During the project period (2017-2021), a new methodological learning content development model was introduced, tested in pilot schools, and integrated into vocational teacher training. The methodological renewal research linked the content development of vocational training within the collaborative learning framework to the modernization of teacher training and multi-levelled e-learning solutions for the knowledge transfer process (Benedek, 2020; Benedek, 2021; Sik, 2018). Furthermore, the learning content development process evolved within this model during student/teacher collaborative activities. On the one hand, the research was theoretically focused on the teacher support of the collaborative learning processes of ICT-based curriculum development in 12 pilot schools and the teacher training and further training that supports this. On the other hand, procedures were introduced, described, and analyzed in which

new technologies (cloud services, mobile communication devices, forms of network cooperation) were also connected to curriculum development.

Concerning international tendencies, the rapid implementation of online collaborative teaching methods were recognized in the VET systems after the economic drop of the latest decade. (Cedefop, 2020). Booming economies have leading practice in this field, which came over the crisis due to an extraordinarily intense and target-focused process that included the renewal of education and vocational training (Colons & Halverson, 2009). According to the technology-driven methodological modernization (Collins, 2008), especially in VET, our project set the following research questions: *how can rapidly changing learning content be, and how could learning be made more effective by increasing student activity within relatively narrow time frames?*

Our project, initially launched in 2016, looking for an answer to the above problem, had to face even more of the latest challenges of online education by 2020 due to the pandemic. The realization of education in a virtual environment and the issues of collaborative development of the curriculum have already occupied researchers in the last decade (Hamutoglu et al., 2020; Hod & Sagi, 2019); however, the reality, due to the impact of Covid-19, exceeds all prior expectations appeared in practice with dynamics.

In our case, in Hungary, between 2020-2022, a radical reduction by two-thirds of the vocational qualification system (to 174 basic qualifications) was introduced, and new output requirements were applied in VET. So far, the subject system and the initiation of new program plans and conditions have been the essential content elements of the transformation. All this initiated a short period of total renewal of content in the reorganized VET institutions (centers and affiliated schools) in 2020-2021. At that time, even the pandemic crisis meant a significant challenge to change the training methodology. In this process construction of micro-contents became an efficient new tool (Sun et. al., 2020). In the first stage of our research, we conducted a needs analysis among the potential stakeholders and international comparative studies. Then, we developed the open content construction model based on theoretical research.

The development of methodological knowledge and the collaborative organization of learning was put into the focus of our work because the open learning resources with active student participation are apt to improve professional knowledge. According to our pilot school experiences, the new-type learning support can considerably improve the effectiveness, organization, and methods of learning. The methodological specialty of the research was model creation based on theoretical analyses, which served as the ground for the implementation of learning resource development tasks with the involvement of engineer and economics vocational teacher students. The surveys and interviews made with these students and the implementation of the micro-contents developed by the students can be considered a new approach to training content improvement as an innovative process. Involving the students (future vocational teachers) in the open learning resource development process and equipping them with methodological knowledge was suitable for the permanent development of active learning.

2 Creating open learning materials becomes high demand

According to the rethinking pedagogy for the digital age (Beetham & Sharpe, 2019), this project presents a new orientation about the first innovative initiatives in the direction of a new methodological learning content development model. A further innovation possibility appeared in the provision of cloud services, assuring the background storage capacity necessary for this process. During the latest decade, it has become a general development trend, which strengthened considerably during the pandemic, to provide mass access to educational content, which is by today supported by excellent and interactive online platforms. The LMS (Learning Management System) and their application of the academic frameworks in VET are justified by the high number of participants, trained in integrated organizations and their various vocational

distribution. In the empirical phase of the research, we support purposeful, open curriculum developments in twelve pilot schools and the framework of university professional teacher training. The model analyzed these results, and in the professional teacher training program, we adapted the procedure and created a broader teacher training program in which we trained 170 teachers.

3 Priority of the local innovation in VET

Using the new methodology, the participating vocational teachers played an influential multiplier role in the highlighted development programs and local innovation implemented at the institutional level. The national regulatory frameworks changed, preferably during the project period. As a result, new conditions appeared amongst the qualification and output requirements of the vocational teacher training programs in terms of the competence field related to methodological and vocational knowledge, the planning of the pedagogical process, the support, organization, and direction of learning, and the evaluation of the educational methods.

Between 2020-2022 in the frame of our university vocational teacher training courses (Digital Pedagogy and Theory of the Training), we applied the open content development method to support collaborative learning directly and with thematic focuses. For further analyses, a more significant set of micro-contents (279 learning units) was outworked within the given courses (*Fig 1*), which had a special significance in the current situation and offered the opportunity for collaborative construction and evaluation within the frameworks of student activities.

Figure 1

Distribution of micro-content VET fields

4 Integration of mobile phones and applications

Mobile phone usage and applications have become more prevalent in recent years. The global trends show that internet usage from desktops started to decrease, while internet usage from mobile phones started to increase in the 2010s, reaching parity by the end of 2016. According to the statistics of statcounter.com, in Hungary, the desktop and mobile market share reached parity in 2021. The share is around 63% mobile and 36% desktop usage (tablet 1%).

Network as a conceptual factor has become the core element of the new methodological developments and the organization of work contacts. Its importance in creating the development model of local innovation was of strategic significance. As a result of the organizational transformation, the VET system became more integrated and size-economic. Simultaneously,

we also experienced the fluctuation of vocational teachers and institutional leaders during the project, which caused several personal changes at the school practice level. In this respect, our research program represented the aspects of life-long learning. In addition to formal education, it also dealt with the development of non-formal learning and permanent training.

Our experience in the twelve pilot schools and the university was an important motive that we have to consider the usage habits of the newer generations as well, who would use their mobile phones for almost everything instead of sitting in front of a desktop computer or a notebook. Therefore, we developed a mobile phone application that can be used both by teachers and students. Furthermore, a mobile application also involves the bring your own device (BYOD) approach into the classrooms, as the students can open the micro-contents pre-created by the teachers, or the students can create micro-contents during the class based on the learned curriculum, which can be done in a competitive or gamified approach as well.

This application extends the functionality of our VET system called Micropedia (*Fig 2 and 3*) by enabling the users to create micro-contents with their mobile phones, using the built-in camera for taking pictures, the touch screen for drawing, and the microphone to record and transcribe texts. Furthermore, the application supports the proper categorization of the different micro-contents, such as assigning the rating, the level, the major, the minor, and the subject of the related qualifications in the VET.

Figure 2

Micropedia – Platform for Community Curriculum Development in Vocational Education (www.mikrotartalom.hu)

Figure 3
Usage of Micropedia

Connecting micro-contents and creating a sequential curriculum, called micro-content paths, is also possible. The users can reach and study the micro-contents and paths of other users and even rate them on a five-star scale. The application also has a built-in web browser so the users can follow the links embedded into the micro-contents to extend their knowledge and do further research.

5 Conclusions

Our research highlighted how Hungary's vocational qualification system changed in the last few years. We presented how we reacted and adapted to the changes during our project by customizing our methodological learning content development model. The model includes the increasing importance of micro-contents and open learning materials. An institutional network was established when collaborating with pilot schools and university teacher training. The teachers and the students successfully applied the new model to their teaching-learning habits, including the older desktop-based and the newer mobile phone and application-based approaches. The statistics of our online platform shows that 18% of the users are browsing and using it from a mobile phone, 1% uses tablet, and 81% of the users are visiting Micropedia from desktop computer. To ensure the sustainability of this innovation process and the project results, the new mobile communication environment based on networks and cloud services offers new applications daily for evaluation and analysis of the learning resources and micro-contents created via collaborative pedagogical activity. These results and further dissemination may act as considerable innovation, motivation, and support for vocational education and training.

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Biographical notes

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